

Designing a Supplementary Reading Using Cultural Language Learning Approach (CLLA)

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Abstract

This paper reports on a project findings concerning the design of a Supplementary Reading Book using Cultural Language Learning Approach (CLLA). The project was conducted in Yogyakarta, Indonesia that generally aimed at designing supplementary reading materials using CLLA as a guide book for tourist guides who worked for Sonobudoyo Museum. The book is entitled "The Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum (JCHRSM)". This utilized a developmental research design, which consisted of three procedures, namely: (1) exploration, aiming to analyze the needs of the tour guides of Sonobudoyo Museum; (2) development, to design a supplementary reading guide book for the (candidate) tourist guides working for Sonobudoyo Museum; and (3) validation, to find the designed guide book accuracy. This study found: (1) The tour guides' needs was JCHRSM using CLLA; (2) the designed book was matched with the tour guides' needs; and (3) the designed guide book was judged accurate and compatible for Sonobudoyo tour guides. This was judged accurate since: (1) it was designed based on the results of the tour guide needs analysis and book's content analysis as suggested by McDonough and McDonough; (2) the 12 times cyclical treatments resulted continually learning improvement on the trainees' reading skills; and (3) the guide book validation through statistical analysis using Mean Difference (M_d) formula and One-shot study experimental design yielded significant gain score between the average score of pretest and post-test, i.e. $8.2 > 5.6$. Besides, the result of FGD (Focus Group Discussion) also indicated that the supplementary reading guide book was recommended as an alternative reference especially for Sonobudoyo tour guides.

Keywords: ELT; CLLA; developmental research; tourist guides; cultural heritages;

1. Introduction

Globalization era has been currently affecting many aspects of human life development, including in English Language Teaching (ELT). Language teaching cannot be separated from culture teaching since language is a part of human's culture. Similarly, culture and technology have constantly expanding in line with technological innovation and knowledge. Thus, the advance of knowledge and technology may affect cultural contact through community meetings in the coffee shops until on line contacts. Besides, the huge amount of migration by economic reasons may also result cultural exchange.

Contacts of various communities with their varied cultures can result in blurring of cultural ownership. Such condition may affect on nation or community's sense of belonging towards its cultural heritage and

trigger conflict of interest among the nations such as for instance, the claims of several songs, traditional dances and clothing as it had ever happened between Malaysia and Indonesia. This case may endanger the unity among the nations in the world. This issue can be solved among other, through English language teaching (ELT), since English is considered as a global language which is learned by most of the people around the world. ELT is possible to be conducted through the existence of English book, including supplementary reading in which content is relevant with the learners' interests.

English language learners can be categorized into two groups, namely those who are learning in the formal schools and in the non-formal boards or institutions. The latter group typically receives less attention from language educators. They are learners who are joining English training for certain interests, including the tour guides who were involved in this project.

Thus, this study attempted to facilitate the tour guides (typically who worked for Sonobudoyo National Museum) English training by designing a guide book that was considered appropriate with their needs in providing communicative services especially for the foreign tourists visiting the museum. The need on the reading materials as a guidance for the tour guides was urgent, since most of them could not communicate in English, whereas such competence was needed to provide communicative services concerning the cultural heritages stored in the museum.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Reading and Supplementary Reading Materials

Reading is a part of language skills which is learnt through various types of discourses for the sake of getting new information available in the written discourses through the content comprehension. This type of language skill is useful both to enhance the readers language learning target, skill, and knowledge. Unfortunately, there is currently a limited number of reading modules available for ESL teachers to teach reading comprehension (Javed et al., 2015: 141) moreover, the availability of supplementary reading for the interests of tour guides. The researcher therefore, attempted to develop a supplementary reading book which was called 'The Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum (The JCHRSM)' as a comprehensive guidelines and effective reading strategies as the basic of doing their jobs easily. The comprehensive guideline was performed by providing relevant questions related to the target knowledge to be taught, while the reading strategies were developed through the questions related to the learners' ability in 'scanning', 'referring', 'inferring' and 'skimming' the linguistics learning target. In this case, all of the given discourses in the book were taught extensively, appropriately with the tour guides' needs.

2.2 Culture and Cultural Language Learning Approach

In general, the term "culture" is connected with the beliefs, values, mind-sets, and practices of a group of people. It includes the behavior pattern and norms of that group the rules, the assumptions, the perceptions, and the logic and reasoning that are specific to a group. In the 20th century, "culture" emerged as a central concept in anthropology, encompassing the range of human phenomena that cannot be attributed to genetic inheritance. Specifically, the term "culture" in American anthropology had two

meanings, id est.: (1) the evolved human capacity to classify and represent experiences with symbols, and to act imaginatively and creatively; and (2) the distinct ways that people living differently classified and represented their experiences, and acted creatively. Hoebel (1982) describes culture as an integrated system of learned behavior patterns which are characteristic of the members of a society and which are not a result of biological inheritance.

Every community or nation has its own unique culture. The distinctions are currently made between the physical artifacts created by a society, its so-called material culture, and everything else, the intangibles such as language and customs that are **the main referent** of the term "culture". Strictly speaking, culture is the result of the interpretation of the human mind to fulfill the purposes and activities of life (Ramli, 2017).

In accordance with the relation between culture and language, Jiang (2010) concluded that language and culture are so closely inter-dependent that neither can be learned without the other. Language learning is normally considered to be a conscious process which consists of committing to memory of information relevant to what is being learned (Tomlinson, 1998: 4). While "culture is an intellectual expressions of human's mind, thought, customs and physical artifacts created **by society**". In a nutshell, it can be defined that Cultural Language Learning (CLL) is a conscious process in acquiring language being learnt through knowledge acquisition about culture of a certain language users' community.

Based on the several views of the aforementioned definitions, it can be synthesized that "Culture is an intellectual expressions of human's mind, thought, customs and physical artifacts created by society". This definition is used as the basic of designing the book's title. The artifacts were created by the ancestors especially available in Yogyakarta, Indonesia such as: various kinds of *wayang*, *batik*, *keris*, *gamelan* orchestra, traditional wedding dress, and *joglo* house. They are considered unique and cannot be found anywhere else. They should be preserved and protected to avoid getting lost, extinction or claimed by other nations that may trigger conflict. Conserving cultural heritages may be realized through the existence of cultural reference books that can be read both by the young generation, other culture community and foreigners. For the sake of providing such kind of reference, supplementary reading materials are needed.

2.3 Reading Materials Design using CLLA

In relation to supplementary materials design, Tomlinson (1998: xiii) stated that supplementary materials are designed to be used in addition to the core materials of a course. They are usually related to the development of skills of reading, writing, listening or speaking rather than to the learning of language items. Related to the definition as written above, supplementary reading may in this case, not only be used **to** enhance readers' reading skills but also may enrich their insights either through formal or autonomous learning.

This project was done to provide a supplementary reading book for the sake of helping the museum tourist guides in running their duties as information providers, since most of them could not communicate in English fluently. The alternative reading book was crucially needed to complete the available

brochures that neither completely performed the various types of the artifacts stored in the museum, nor represented the complete information concerning to the museum.

The designed reading materials were developed in contemporary, appropriately with the development of current ELT concept and using Cultural Language Learning Approach (CLLA). In accordance with approach, Brown (1994:51) stated that an approach is theoretical positions and beliefs about the nature of language learning, and the applicability of both pedagogical settings (Theory of language and language learning). In this study, CLLA is an approach which focuses on the discourse content that contains knowledge about various kinds of Javanese cultural heritage (such as *keris*, *gamelan* orchestra, various types of *wayang*, *Joglo* house, traditional wedding dress, and dances) as currently provided in Sonobudoyo National Museum, where the artefacts have been collected and preserved.

Figure 1. English Curriculum Principle (FGD TEFLIN, 2013)

The reading materials explored various kinds of discourses which aimed at improving the users’ reading skills and to cultivate their knowledge about Javanese culture all at once. Beside several considerations as written above, the book was also designed by referring to the concept of language teaching, which involves the four aspects of aim/goals, learning materials, learning process and its assessment as suggested by FGD TEFLIN (2013). Figure 1 shows the principle of English curriculum according to FGD TEFLIN.

In the learning process, the participants were introduced to the vocabularies related to culture and the wares stored in the museum. Thus, the cultural language was learnt through the reading materials as an approach to develop participants’ reading skills through the vocabularies they have acquired, namely any words related to the existence of *wayang*, *batik*, *keris*, *gamelan* orchestra, traditional wedding dress, and *Joglo* house.

The learning process involved 20 tourist guides who worked for the museum. They were involved to join English reading comprehension class for 14 meetings. At last they were assessed to find the data of their learning achievement progress, as one of the criteria to judge whether the designed supplementary reading book was appropriate with their needs and was able to enhance their reading skills for the sake of conducting their jobs as tourist guides of Sonobudoyo Museum easily.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Participants

As it has been mentioned earlier, this project was conducted in Yogyakarta, Indonesia and generally aimed at designing a guide book for tourist guides (also the candidates) in order to be able to provide normative information services for foreign tourists visiting Sonobudoyo Museum Yogyakarta, Indonesia and for other users. The book is called “The Javanese Cultural Heritage Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum (The JCHRSM)”. To gain the main research objective, this project involved 20 tourist guides who currently worked for the museum. As an early added information, though they ran their duties to provide communicative services especially for foreigners, ironically, most of them could not speak English fluently. So far, they served foreigners by a little speaking or, even, keeping silent.

3.2 Design

Appropriately with the research’s objective, this study used a developmental research design which is also called research and development (R and D). In case of R&D, Gall & Gall (2003: 569) which was also referred by Sukmadinata (2007: 163), stated that educational R and D is an industry-based development model in which the findings of research are used in designing new products and procedures, which then are systematically tested, evaluated, and refined until they meet specified criteria of effectiveness, quality, or similar standards. The product is considered effective, qualified and standardized if it fulfills the three conceptual aspects of designing reading materials. The product effectiveness or compatibility was defined through interpreting the result of testing on the participants’ reading comprehension that was then, analyzed statistically to find its validity using Product Moment Correlation formula. The quality and the standard of the reading materials were judged through the content analysis as it was suggested by McDonough and McDonough (1997). Such criteria were used as the basic in judging the compatibility of the supplementary reading materials as the product of this project.

The procedure of this project was inspired by Sukmadinata’s (2007: 190) research and development procedure who has simplified Gall & Gall’s (2003) ten procedures of conducting developmental research or research and development, namely: (a) research and information collecting; (b) planning; (c) preliminary product development; (d) preliminary field testing; (e) main product revision; (f) main field testing; (g) operational product revision; (h) operational field testing; (i) final product revision; and (j) dissemination and implementation into three procedures, namely: (a) exploration, (b) development, and (c) experimental or evaluation stage.

Referring to the three stages of conducting research and development (R & D) as it is written above, this project was carried out into three procedures, namely: (a) exploration, aiming to analyze the vision and missions of the cultural heritage and the users’ needs towards the book’s content; (b) development, for the intention of designing a prototype in which content matched with the aim or the missions of the existence of cultural heritage and the users’ needs; (c) experimental or evaluation stage which was in the form of validation of the relevant stakeholders, to legalize the design accuracy.

Within the exploration stage, the participants were interviewed to get the data related to their needs or their issues during their working times. Needs assessment (which is also called needs analysis) is the discrepancy between an existing set of conditions and a desired set of conditions which among others can

be used to determine the deficits exist so that they can be addressed (Gall & Gall, 2003: 557; Cohen et al., 2000: 390). In this study, needs analysis was used to determine the deficits exist of the provision of a guide book for tourist guides and foreign tourist which meets the vision and missions and users' needs (namely Sonobudoyo tourist guides) in the research setting.

The development stage consisted of 20 participants who were all involved in cyclical treatments in the form of reading comprehension training. The training was held for 14 meetings by utilizing the designed book as the materials to discuss. In the evaluation stage, they were tested especially on their reading skills acquisition related to their jobs.

3.3 Instruments

As it is written above that this project was conducted through three procedures, namely: exploration, development and validation. The instruments used in this case were as follows.

Firstly, at the exploration stage it employed structured interview for the intention of collecting information on the users' needs in providing normative communicative services especially for foreigners visiting Sonobudoyo Museum. In principle, structured interview is like questionnaire that is administered orally and provided detailed data comparable across informants (Nunan & Bailey, 2011: 313). It is intended to control data reliability, by giving some similar questions addressed to every respondent or research subject to avoid data bias (Cohen *et al.*, 2000). In this project, interview was addressed to all of the tourist guides working for Sonobudoyo Museum. In this case, 20 persons of tour guides were purposively involved as the research participants.

Secondly, at the development stage, this study used documentation as the research's instrument, observation as the data collection method completed with field note as the instrument to collect the data. Documentation was conducted by compiling all documents which were in the forms of the relevant books and brochures available at the library of the museum. Observation was done towards the process of English language training held for 14 meetings cyclically. The result of observation was noted in the field notes to analyze their contents, whether or not the available documents fulfilled the needs of the tour guides who especially provided communicative services for foreigners.

Third, at the experimental or evaluation stage, the instruments used were test (consisted of pretest and posttest) and FGD (Focus Group Discussion) decision towards the appropriateness of the research product that is called: "The Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum" (The JCHRSM). FGD is one of the research instruments which consist of a group of relevant interest or field guided by a moderator or facilitator aiming at discussing a certain issue in a lively and natural discussion amongst themselves for the sake of gaining an agreement for the issue solution. This tool is commonly used to judge an agreement or the disagreement through their various insights toward a certain survey findings that cannot be analyzed statistically (ODI, 2009).

In this case, the FGD involved 8 (eight) relevant stakeholders such as: the office head and 5 staffs of the museum, a librarian and the author herself, as the researcher for collecting data. The group was given 10 (ten) items of questions related to their opinion towards 'The JCHRSM' through a structured interview. The results were then, analyzed by using Aiken's V (See Figure 3) formula as suggested by Azwar (2016:

134-135). The next stage after collecting data using the above mentioned instruments was analyzing each data procedurally.

3.4 Data Analysis

The data in this project consisted of primary and secondary data. The primary data were in the form of the results of: (*in-depth*) interview, documentation, cyclical observation, reading comprehension test and focus group discussion (FGD) validation consisting of the head and the relevant staffs and the author as the data collector. The FGD was involved to validate the understudied tourist guide book toward the appropriateness of the book’s content with the institution missions and the users’ needs. The secondary data were in the form of any books provided in the research setting (*i.e.* a national museum which stored and preserved various kinds of Javanese cultural heritage) and the understudied supplementary reading prototype especially designed for the tourist guides working for Sonobudoyo Museum. The gathered data was analyzed through the following activities.

Firstly, the first primary data, such as the results of (*in-depth*) interview, documentation, cyclical observation and the FGD were analyzed using Aiken’s V formula (See Figure 3). The reading comprehension pre-test and post-test results were analyzed statistically using mean difference or gain score computations. Secondly, the secondary data *i.e.* the available documents were analyzed using content analysis of McDonough & McDonough Model (1997). The documents were analyzed descriptively and validated through peers’ debriefing (by checking the truth of the obtained data to persons who were not directly involved in the research) and tri-angulation theory.

Peer debriefing, which is also called analytic triangulation, is the process whereby a researcher calls upon a disinterested peer, that is a peer who is not involved in the research project to aid in probing the researcher's thinking around all or parts of the research process. This probing includes, but it is not limited to, methodology, interpretation, and analysis of data. As such, it is regarded as one of a complement of techniques used to enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of qualitative research through the use of external peers. It is often compared to or paralleled with internal validity in quantitative research (ThếNguyin, 2013).

Figure 2. Procedures on Data Analysis Model (McDonough & McDonough, 1997: 118)

The procedures on analyzing data in this research used the following stages. The first stage was needs analysis, that means analyzing the result of interviewing the participants (id est. the tourist guides) and the result of the content analysis of the provided documents using McDonough & McDonough (1997: 118) content analysis model. The available documents stored in the museum were mostly in the form of brochures which only performed several pictures such as *keris*, *wayang*, *gamelan*, Bedoyo dance, traditional wedding dress, and *Joglo* house, without any complete explanations concerning each of the heritage, whereas the more complete information related to the heritages may provide complete data that must be needed by the tourists, especially the relevant foreign researchers.

The content analysis was addressed to all of the understudied variable, such as: (a) variable of the research participants’ understanding towards the content of the designed book and its characteristics; (b) variable of the participants’ issues in using the designed book as an alternative instrument to provide normative communicative services concerning with the existence of the cultural heritages stored in Sonobudoyo Museum; (c) variable of documentation and the training process held in Sonobudoyo Museum Yogyakarta; and (d) variable of the participants’ learning achievement assessment. The gained data, then, was analyzed descriptively by using Aiken’s V formula as shown at Figure

$S = r - lo$ <p>(1)</p>	$V = \sum S / [n (c-1)]$ <p>(2)</p>
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Figure 3. Aiken’s V Formula (Azwar, 2016)

Notes:

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|---|---|
| Lo= The lowest item score of validity (= 1) | S = Scorer/Rater |
| c = The highest item score of validity (5) | n = The number of rater/s |
| r = The score given by a rater | V=Coefficient number of content validity stretching from 0.00 to 1.00 |

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1 Findings

This part performs the answers of the three research questions as it was formulated at the beginning of this paper. As it is written previously that this project generally aimed at designing a needed book as an alternative reference for the tourist guides of foreigners for the sake of providing information services concerning with the cultural heritages reserved in Sonobudoyo museum. This was done since there was not any reference available in that site except brochures. Specifically, this study investigated: (1) the needs assessment of the tourist guides of Sonobudoyo Museum reading materials; (2) the type of the reading materials design needed by the tourist guides of Sonobudoyo; and (3) the appropriateness or the compatibility of the designed reading materials towards the tourist guides working for Sonobudoyo Museum. Having completed analyzing all of the gathered data using both content and statistical analyses as it was clarified previously, this study found the following information.

Firstly, the needs of the tourist guides of Sonobudoyo Museum were reading materials which performed vocabularies related to cultural heritages available in the museum. The reading materials which was in

the form of a handy book called “Javanese Cultural Heritage Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum” (The JCHRSM) was needed to help the tourist guides working for the museum. The book provides any information dealing with the cultural heritage content stored in the museum. Besides, to inform about the provided artifacts collection needs the mastery of knowledge related to each collection types. As it is written above that Sonobudoyo Museum preserves various kinds of artifacts especially Javanese cultural heritages such as: various types of *wayang*, *batik*, *keris*, *gamelan* orchestra, traditional wedding dress, traditional dances and *Joglo* house that are considered unique and specific for they cannot be found at other places except in Java Island, Indonesia. To introduce the available collections as mentioned above, the tourist guides as the main stakeholders should have acquired the “what”, “why” and “how” principles of the artifact collections. The “what” is related to the descent and the use of the artifact, the “why” is related with the philosophical feature and the “how” is about the procedures on producing the investigated objects. The book model was designed to fulfill such user’s needs *i.e.* by providing information that contains the three aspects as mentioned above.

Secondly, the needed type of the reading materials design was a handy guide book which covered all of the cultural heritages information (presented using Cultural Language Learning Approach or CLLA in short). The JCHRSM was considered compatible either for the users (especially the tour guides who worked for the museum) or the vision and mission of the museum (that is, supporting Yogyakarta Province to realize its vision as a leading province in the fields of education, culture, and tourism in Southeast Asia in 2025. Sonobudoyo, which is located in Yogyakarta Province, must, of course, contribute such provincial vision among others through running of the missions in preserving its cultural heritages by storing the artifacts in the museum. To support the heritages preservation can be realized through the provision of the book which provides any information concerning with the heritages. As an illustration, the content of the designed book is presented at Table 1.

Table 1: The linguistic content of ‘The Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sono budoyo Museum (JCHRSM)’

The designed target skill	Page	Language content
	1-3	Javanese Culture Heritages
	3-5	Sonobudoyo Museum
	6-7	Vision and Mission of Sonobudoyo Museum
Reading Comprehension	7-40	Sonobudoyo Collections
	41- 43	Traditional Javanese House (<i>Joglo</i> House)
	44	The Clapper Caller Gods
	44-55	Masks and Their Origins
	56-60	Batik and Its Types
	61-64	<i>Bedhaya</i> Dance

Table 1 depicts the book’s content which explores linguistic and its language target. It consists of 64 pages and includes various discourses, namely: Javanese Culture Heritages, Sonobudoyo Museum, vision

and mission of Sonobudoyo Museum, Sonobudoyo Collections, Traditional Javanese House (*Joglo* house), The Clapper Caller Gods, Masks and Their Origins, Batik and Its Types, and *Bedhaya* Dance. It was considered matched with the users, for the designed model was created by considering the deficits exist of the provision of a guide book for tourist guides and foreign tourists which really met the defined vision and missions of the cultural heritage museum. It also provides the “what”, “why” and “how” about various kinds and features of *wayang*, *batik*, *keris*, *gamelan* orchestra, traditional wedding dress, *Joglo* house and Javanese traditional dances. Such book’s contents were intentionally presented to enrich the readers’ knowledge about the existence of such valuable heritages. Besides, it is also possible to use as an alternative reference both for English language learners and/or teachers to facilitate English language learning using cultural language learning approach or CLLA in short.

Third, the designed reading materials was judged compatible to be used as a guidance for the tourist guides who worked for Sonobudoyo Museum. This judgment was decided by considering the result of focus group discussion (FGD) decision concerning the compatibility of the book towards the users’ needs. The book was agreed to be used as guidance for the tourist guides of Sonobudoyo in providing information services for foreigners. By utilizing the book, they may run their jobs easily. The result of the FGD is illustrated at Table 2.

Table 2: The Result of FGD decision analysis using percentage point
(Inspired by Hutchinson & Waters, 1994)

No	Statements	Item	Yes	%	No	%
1. Audience /Users	The designed book (JCHRSM) is appropriate to be used by the tourist guides working for Sonobudoyo Museum.	1	5	62.5	3	37.5
	The designed book (JCHRSM) fulfills the tourist guides need on the lack of such handy guide book to make them easier to handle their daily jobs.	2	6	75	2	25
	The designed book may be used as an alternative reference to help the tourist guides to provide communicative services especially for foreigners.	3	6	75	2	25
2. Aim/ Objectives	The aim of the provision of the book matched with the vision and mission of the existence of Sonobudoyo Museum.	4	7	87.5	1	12.5
	The aim of the provision of the book matched with the needs on the existence of non-brochures written information about Sonobudoyo Museum.	5	6	75	2	25
3. Content	The designed book performs the needed information concerning with the cultural heritages stored in Sonobudoyo Museum.	6	7	87.5	1	12.5

The provided discourses support the users/tourist guides language acquisition	7	8	100	0	0
The designed book is interesting, handy to carry around so that it is very helpful for the users to provide information related to the cultural heritages stored in Sonobudoyo Museum.	8	7	87.5	1	12.5

Table 2 illustrates 8 (eight) questions addressed to the 8 (eight) FGD members. The questions were categorized into three aspects; they are audience/users, aim/objectives and content (inspired by Hutchinson & Waters, 1994). The ‘audience’ category consisted of 3 statements, the ‘aim/objectives’ category consisted of 2 statements, and the ‘content’ category which had 3 statements. The first item was supported by 5 members, while the second and the third were agreed by six members for each. The 4th (fourth) and the 5th (fifth) were agreed by 7 and 6 members for each, while the 6th (sixth), the 7th (seventh) and the 8th (eighth) items were supported by 7, 8, 7 members for each. Based on the computation result using percentage, it was found that the average percentage of the achieved data was 625: 8 members = 78.125% or 0.78 in the decimal number. Such coefficient number is categorized high.

To control the data analysis validation quality, the author intentionally carried on a triangulation. Conceptually, there are four types of triangulation. The first is ‘data triangulation’; in which different source of data (such as teachers, students, parents, et cetera) contribute to an investigation. Secondly, ‘theory triangulation’ is used when various theories are brought to bear in a study. The third is ‘researcher triangulation’, in which more than one researcher contributes to the investigation. Finally, ‘methods triangulation’ involves the use of multiple methods, such as interviews, questionnaire, observation schedules, test scores, and field notes. In this case, triangulation theories were used by considering that it matched with the investigated issue.

The theory used to compare in this study was the ‘pedagogical scaffolding’. According to Springer (2003) and Nunan & Bailey (2011: 2013), triangulation theory may include ‘project-based learning’, ‘pedagogical scaffolding and contingent language use’. Here, the alternative pedagogical scaffolding was the use of two scaffoldings of Hutchinson & Waters (1994) theory of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) materials design and McDonough & McDonough theory of Content Analysis. The results of utilizing those two theories were analyzed using percentage and Aiken’s V formula. Table 3 depicts the result of content validity computation using Aiken’s V formula.

Table 3: The Result of FGD decision analysis using Aiken’s V Formula
(Inspired by Azwar, 2016)

Number of Item	Raters saying “Yes”	$V = \sum S/[n (c-1)]$
1	5	0.60
2	6	0.75
3	6	0.75
4	7	0.89
5	6	0.75
6	7	0.89
7	8	1.00
8	7	0.89
	$\sum V =$	6.52
	Coefficient average =	0.81

As it can be seen at Table 3, the coefficient average score data computation was 0.81. This data was gained from a number of raters (from the totally 8 FGD members) who answered ‘Yes’ (meaning agreed or supported the given statements within the structured interview). Based on the total gained score of 6.52 with the total FGD member of 8 persons, it means that the coefficient number of the product validity was 0.81. If it is compared with the first data, that is 0.78, the second computation result using Aiken’s V formula was higher ($0.81 > 0.78$). Even though there was a little different of the results but the score gap was not significantly different by considering that both of the coefficient numbers were around 0.8 that categorized high validity coefficient. As it is known that the validity coefficient number stretches from 0.00 to 1.00 (Arikunto, 2010). The judgment of the FGD then was used as the legalization of publishing the book.

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1. Cultural Language Learning Approach and Its Implementation

It has been defined at the early part of this work, that Cultural Language Learning Approach (CLLA) is an approach which focuses on the discourse content that contains knowledge about various kinds of a certain community cultural heritage. In accordance with such concept, Hermayawati (2014) suggested language teachers, instructors and trainers who are part of education system to support the government policy in its effort to solve the people’s moral values degradation and for the sake of introducing local cultures towards young generation and foreigners aiming at preventing conflicts due to the wrong recognition on the available certain heritages. She proposed that any information (the ‘what’, ‘why’, ‘where’ and ‘how’) concerning with the chosen cultural heritages can be embedded within the discourses both as the linguistic and the knowledge learning targets simultaneously.

Say as an example, the term ‘*wayang*’ (puppets) has a relatively broad connotation. This word may involve the ‘what’, ‘why’, ‘where’ and ‘how’ aspects that commonly accompany its existence. The ‘what’ term may involve the terms ‘*dalang*’ (puppeteer), ‘*gamelan*’ (orchestra), ‘*niyaga*’ (gamelan musician), ‘*pesinden*’ (Javanese singer), ‘*lakon*’ (story title). The term ‘why’ relates to reasons of the relevant community like this art. The term ‘where’ is connoted with the place of

performing the show and/or the original descent of the term. And the 'how' relates to the way of playing or enjoying it. Similarly, with the existence of the other related terms such as: 'keris', 'batik', traditional wedding dress, 'Joglo' house, and 'Bedhaya dance' are described completely by including the 'what', 'why', 'where' and 'how' aspects. In a nutshell, all information related to the cultural heritages as written above may be used as the means of developing both the linguistic and knowledge of learners or users for such information need through the supplementary reading book content comprehension.

CLLA is actually not only beneficial to use as an approach to enhance reading skill, but also can be used for the three other skills, namely listening, speaking and writing. But in this project, the main intention was to provide an alternative reference aiming to help the tourist guides jobs in running their duties. Here, the needed terms to fulfill were both information and the relevant language components such as vocabulary, pronunciation, spelling, structure and grammar. But all of the components were not isolatedly exposed but integratedly embedded within the reading skill mastery. Hence, the use of CLLA as an approach will depend on the learning process objectives.

4.2.2 Establishing English Learning for Non-academic Need

It is undeniable that English teaching today, including teaching reading, is still mainly in favor of academic interests and less in favor of the non-academic ones. Whereas, the latter needs more attention from the academicians to serve since the non-academicians commonly earn the living in the informal sectors with the relative huge amount of numbers. The tour guides, for instance, if working in the formal sector such as those are hired by their institution, they are commonly positioned as a contract workers whose fate depend on the quality of their works. If their works are acceptable or considered professional, their contracts will be extended. In facts, as tour guides whose primary jobs were providing communicative services for foreigners, they should be able to do their jobs professionally, at least by utilizing the supplementary reading book that has been designed using CLLA.

Such type of workers need more attention, even though they had ever learnt English for many years before working as tourist guides, *i.e.* whenever they were at several years of elementary schools until the higher level of study. Normatively, such types of workers are categorized into false-beginners level. According to Bailey (2005: 14), a false-beginner level is a learner who had learnt English for many years but keep unable to communicate in the language s/he learnt for many years. The investigated tourist guides were, in this case, included in these types of learners.

Considering the tourist guides level of learning, the author treated them as the false-beginners. They were taught reading aloud beside comprehension, though conceptually, reading aloud should be taught for the beginners and pre-intermediate level in which mostly at the age of children and young learners. Reading aloud was explored to improve the participants' pronunciation mastery while reading comprehension was intended to enhance the learners reading skill, especially in understanding the provided discourse contents. The other language aspects such as lexis, grammar and structure were learnt integratively within the given discourses sequentially from the easiest to the more complicated. Traditionally, syllabus items were graded and sequenced according to grammatical complexity for instance, the simple present tense would be introduced before conditional sentences (Nunan, 2009: 95).

In relation to reading comprehension there was the dilemma captured, for instance, the text readability was really influenced by linguistic factors like words difficulty and its sentences complexity. Thus, this became a challenge for the author (as the instructor) in choosing the worthiest strategy to deliver the texts successfully comprehended. Concerning the principle of learning strategy, Nunan (ibid: 89) defined that it involves the mental and communicative process that learners deploy to learn a second language. In this project, the author employed group work strategy to arouse the participants' motivation to lighten their learning process and minimize their burdens. As it is written in the title's part, principally, this project employed Cultural Language Learning Approach (CLLA). This approach was embedded together within the given provided discourses for the group works study as the learning strategy. CLLA was, in this study, by the reason of matching their daily jobs on having moral responsibility to introduce and disseminate the cultural heritages stored in their institution where they were demanded to dedicate or devote their capacities. While the group works strategy was used by the reason of making the learning processes easier for the participants to do every learning task provided by the English language training instructor (the author).

4.2.3 Assessment

Assessment is defined as the process of teacher's gauging information of the learners learning processes and its results. This also involves on multiple ways of collecting information that provide them with the type of feedback the need to monitor learner's progress and to plan for instruction (O'Malley & Pierce, 1996: 2). The term assessment cannot be separated from the term evaluation. As it is known that there are two types of evaluation, they are formative and summative evaluation. Formative evaluation focuses on evaluating the process to improve the learning program while the latter focuses more on the result of the program to measure both the efficiency and the effectiveness of the educational program (Sukmadinata, 2007: 122). According to Nunan (ibid: 140), assessment is defined as procedures for determining what learners can and cannot do, while evaluation is procedures for determining how effectively the curriculum is achieving its objectives. Concerning with language assessment, Fulcher & Davidson (2007: 29) defined that it should be in performance-based. Performance-based elements in large scale are usually restricted to a small number of controlled task types which commonly involves writing and speaking. Referring to the various definitions written above, it can be defined the distinction of assessment and evaluation is, that assessment focuses on gaining information of the learners learning need, while the latter is stressed more on the learning program's effectiveness and efficiency.

In line with the above concepts of assessment, in this study, both assessment and evaluation terms were used as the instruments to gain information concerning with the participants need analysis procedure and the result of their learning process for 14 meetings of English training. In other words, assessment principle was used as the tool to gather need analysis while the latter was utilized to evaluate the participants' language acquisition after joining the intentional treatments based on their performances both in written and spoken way using the designed product, namely the supplementary reading material which is called JCHRSM (Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum).

4.2.4 The Strengths and Weaknesses of the Research Product

As it is considered that there is nothing perfect in the world of life, likewise the designed model of JCHRSM, of course, it has its strengths and weaknesses. The strengths are among others as follows: (1) It fulfills the user's or the reader's needs at his/her curiosity concerning with the Javanese cultural heritages; (2) It provides a new complete reference for further relevant research; (3) It provides information about Javanese cultural heritages that can be beneficial to disseminate and/or declare to other nations through tourism for the sake of avoiding international conflicts which may appear as the effect of the similar culture recognition; (4) It can be used as an alternative supplementary reading in English language teaching (ELT) especially to facilitate the teaching of extensive reading; (5) It may realize and generate the Javanese learners' sense of belonging toward their ancestor's valuable heritage, so that they will be responsible for preserving it as well.

The weaknesses of the model is, among others as follows: (1) It merely contains specified cultural heritages so that it may be only interesting to be read by a certain relevant community; (2) It does not provide any task to evaluate the readers or learners' reading comprehension since it only provides a lot of text concerning with Javanese cultural heritage information; (3) It does not facilitate materials to teach other language skills such as listening, speaking and writing, except it is redeveloped into the teaching of those skills. Thus, it can be only used as a reference related to cultural heritages stored in Sonobudoyo Museum. The provision of such designed book however, was extremely needed to complete the available brochures which were relatively insufficient to fulfill the need of the tour guides in conducting their jobs.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

It has been widely written that the main points of this project was designing a handy book contains any information concerning with the cultural heritages stored in Sonobudoyo Museum Yogyakarta. As it has been written earlier that this study yielded reading book which was called Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum (The JCHRSM). This book was designed and then judged as an alternative guide book for the museum's tourist guides by considering the results of the three variables that had been intentionally used as the basic of the end product decision. Based on the research findings as written above, it can be concluded as follows: (1) The need of the tourist guides currently working for the research setting (namely Sonobudoyo National Museum) was the provision of the guide book entitled "Javanese Cultural Heritages Reserved in Sonobudoyo Museum" (The JCHRSM); (2) Based on the result of the development research, it was found that the understudied book model was matched with the users' need; (3) The result of validation step showed that the book model was judged to be a tourist guide book that can be used as a provision for tourism service. Additionally, this book may be also developed to be a supplementary reading for English language learners and teachers and other users.

As it has been discussed earlier that this primary project finding was the provision of The JCHRSM that was actually dedicated for the relevant tour guides but only as a supporting reference and has not developed fully as normative language teaching materials that contain various tasks to support language training. Therefore, these results still need wider theoretical and practical development, especially for the advanced researcher, language materials developer and teacher of English. On the other hand, this

product may be multiplied by the authorized official in charge for providing alternative written information not only for the workers, but also for the visitors who need the complete information related to the heritages stored in the museum. This is suggested to do by the museum or the upper authorized institution such as the regional government by considering that this project had limited facilities. Ultimately, as a 'no ivory that is not cracked' this paper still needs suggestions from the readers for the sake of its perfection.

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